

Greener Journal of Science, Engineering and Technology Research

ISSN: 2276-7835 Impact Factor 2012 (UJRI): 0.7563 ICV 2012: 5.62

A Survey of Physicochemical and Bacteriological Quality of Pipe-Borne Water Used for Drinking in Rufus Giwa Polytechnic, Owo Ondo State, Nigeria

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Research Article

A Survey of Physicochemical and Bacteriological Quality of Pipe-Borne Water Used for Drinking in Rufus Giwa Polytechnic, Owo Ondo State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

Pipe borne water samples used for drinking in Rufus Giwa Polytechnic, Owo were analysed bacteriologically and physicochemically using standard methods. Four water samples were subjected to physicochemical analyses like PH, temperature, color, turbidity total hardness, dissolve solids, salinity, conductivity total solid, nitrate, sulphate, calcium, and sodium. These properties of the water samples were within the WHO/FAO standard for water except dissolve solids, nitrate chloride and conductivity. The bacteriological analysis was carried out to detect the total mesophilic, coliform count and subsequently, organisms present in the water samples. The total mesophilic count ranged between 2.6×10^4 to 3.3×10^4 cfu/ml while the total coliform count ranged between 1.1×10^3 to 1.6×10^3 cfu/ml. Both values were higher than the month standard limit for drinking water. The identified organisms include; *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Citrobacter*, *sp*, *Proteus sp*, *E.coli*, *Bacillus sp*, *Pseudomonas sp*, *Enterobacter sp*, *klebsiella sp*, *Acinetobacter sp*, *Streptococcus sp* and *Serratia sp*. 70% of the isolates were gram negative and most belonged to the family Enterobacteriaceae. The data suggests the need for treatment of the water samples by the school authority and by simple boiling by the consumers.

KEYWORDS: Physicochemical, Quality, Bacteriological, Pipe-borne water, Analysis.

INTRODUCTION

The World Health Organization estimated that up to 80% of all sickness and diseases in the world are caused by inadequate sanitation, polluted water and unavailability of water (WHO, 1997). Approximately three out of five persons in developing world and only about one in four have any kind of sanitary facilities (Mengesha et al, 2004). Water is a common resource quite abundant in nature but unfortunately not readily available to man in the form desired. Water is fundamentally important to all plants, animals and man (Ajewole, 2005). Water is essential for life and life evolves in water. It is significant due to its unique chemical and physical properties (Obi and Okocha, 2007). The key to increased human productivity and long life is good quality water (Urbansky and Magnuson, 2002). The provision of good quality household for drinking water is often regarded as an important means of improving health. According to World Health Organization (WHO), there are an estimated 4 billion cases of diarrhea and 2.2 million deaths annually (WHO, 2002). The consumption of unsafe water has been implicated as one of the major causes of this disease. Gradual deterioration of water quality resulted from the increase in human population and urbanization (Ho and Hui, 2001). Water of good drinking quality is of basic importance to human physiology and man's continued existence depends very much on its availability (Lamikara, 1999). The provision of potable water to the rural and urban population is necessary to prevent health hazards (Lemo, 2002). Before water can be described as potable, it has to comply with certain physical, chemical and microbiological standards which are designed to ensure that the water is palatable and safe for drinking (Tebutt 1983).

The need for determining the suitability of water for drinking and bathing purposes has been recognized since 1855 when snow and budd related outbreaks of typhoid fever and cholera to water contaminated with faecal wastes (Ajewole, 2005). It is estimated that up to 80% of ill health in developing countries are water and sanitation related (Cheesbrough, 2000). In the year 2000, the estimated global burden of diseases associated with poor water supply equaled more than 2 billion cases of diseases with an annual death than of 2.2 billion (WHO, 2004). Presently, according to the United Nations (UN) more than 5 million people die annually first from diseases caused by unsafe

drinking water and lack of sanitation. The major problems of safe drinking water are those of availability and quality (Ajewole, 2005).

Generally, the sources of water can be grouped into three namely, rain, surface (which include river water, streams, sea water) and underground and ground water (including well water and borehole water) (Oyebode, 2005). The first key step in providing safe drinking water is the selection of the best available source of water that will be the easiest and cheapest to transform into safe drinking water. Piped borne water from boreholes is a ground water in which at least a dept of 150ft is drilled to source for drinking water which is pumped out with the aid of a pumping machine into an overhead tank . It is generally accepted that groundwater from deep aquifers is protected from pathogen contamination by the covering soil layers (Tsen, 1999). The quality of groundwater is a function of natural processes as well as anthropogenic activities. That is to say that ground water (e.g. borehole) is not completely protected from contamination, which could be either microbial or inorganic agent or even due to human activities and environmental conditions (Keswick, 1984).

The aim of this work was to analyze water used for drinking from pipe borne source for its bacteriological and physicochemical qualities and to identify the possible sources of contamination of the water.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Collection Of Water Sample: The pipe-borne water samples were collected from four different points within the institution (Rectors office, Boys hostel, Girls hostel and maintenance department) using sterile 250ml glass bottles that were sterilized using the hot air oven at 160⁰C for 2hours and were covered light and immediately taken to the laboratory and analyzed within 6hours (WHO, 2004).

Bacteriological Analysis of the Water Samples: The water samples were generally diluted and 0.1ml of the four-fold dilution was used for the analysis. For the total mesophilic count, the samples were plated on nutrient agar while MacConkey agar was used for the total coliform count. The plates were placed in an incubator at 37⁰C for 24hours Cheesbrough (2003).

Identification and Characterization of the Isolates: The pure culture of the isolates were identified using the cultural characteristics gram staining reaction, biochemical test and sugar utilization tests as described by Cheesbrough (2003).

Physicochemical Analyses of the Water Samples: Parameters such as turbidity, temperature, PH, conductivity, salinity, total suspended solids, total hardness, acidity and minerals (Sodium, calcium, chloride, nitrate, sulphate) contentment of the water samples were determined using the methods described by Devis and Frectas (1990).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Physicochemical properties of freshly collected pipe-borne water samples used for drinking in Rufus Giwa Polytechnic, Owo are shown in table 1. The parameters analyzed were color, turbidity, conductivity, total hardness, dissolved solid, temperature, salinity, calcium sodium, nitrate, sulphate, chloride, and total solid in all the sources samples, they were within the WHO recommended values of 15 CTU for colour, 0.5NTU for turbidity, 0.5 total hardness, 100mg/ml of calcium, 400 for sulphae, 100 for total solid and 6.5-8.5 for pH (at 25⁰C). The water samples were above the WHO recommended values for conductivity sodium, nitrate chloride, The PH of the water samples were within the WHO recommended for drinking water and domestic purposes as they have PH range of 6.8-7.2 (WHO, 1993). The pH of water could make the water corrosive (at low pH) or result in taste complaints (at high pH). Ali (1991) indicated that the fluctuations in optimum pH ranges may lead to an increase or decrease in the toxicity of poison in water bodies. The turbidity (absorbance reading taken at 540mm wave length) of the water ranges from 0.02-0.04 which is less than 1.00 NTU. WHO (1998) stated that drinking water is best consumed with NTU less than 1.00 for health purposes. It suggests that the appearance of water with a turbidity of less than 5 NTU is usually acceptable to consumers, although may vary with locals. Circumstances of the consumption of highly turbid water may constitute a health risk as excessive turbidity can protect pathogenic microorganisms from the effect of disinfectants, and also stimulate the growth of bacterial during storage as also observed by Zvikomborero (2005). Color is an important physical property of water because of its implication for water supply and the need to reduce it to acceptable levels by water treatment is highly recommended. The color of the water samples were not up to 5 CTU as recommended by WHO for no risk.

Table 1 Physicochemical properties of pipe –borne water used for drinking in Rufus Giwa Polytechnic, Owo, Ondo State, Nigeria.

Parameters	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	M	N	O
WHO standard	15CTU	0.5NTU	250cm ⁻¹	(0.5)	A B	AB	72.2 8	120	200	10	400	AB	250	1000	6.5- 8.5
BOYHOS	6	0.03	245	0.4	0.8	0.6	25	88	230	66	240	0.2	271	601	6.8
GIRLHOS	7	0.03	255	0.3	1.5	0.8	26	95	271	70	270	0.1	248	590	7.1
MAINTE	6	0.04	260	0.2	1.0	0.9	25	90	221	59	209	0.3	250	605	6.7
RECOFF	6	0.02	300	0.3	0.6	0.8	27	79	251	52	220	0.4	288	599	7.2

Key: The water codes were: BOYHOS (Boys hostel) GIRLSHOS (Girls hostel) MAINTE (Maintenance), RECOFF (Rector's Office) AB=Absent, A= color, B=turbidity, C= conductivity, D=Total hardness, E=Total acidity, F=dissolved solid, G=Temperature, H=Calcium, I=Sodium, J=Nitrate, K=Sulphate, L=Salinity, M=Chloride, N=Total solid, O=PH

Color in material water usually results from the leading of organic materials and is primarily the cause of dissolved and colloidal humic substances, primarily humic and felvic acids color is also strongly influenced by the presence of iron and other metals either as neutral impurities or as corrosion products.

Conductivity of the water except for BOYHIS was higher than the recommended value of 250Ns cm⁻¹. The fluctuations in electrical conductivity correlated positively with the total dissolved solids (TDS). Suspended solids (SS) and TDS are common indicators of a polluted water source. According to Zvikomborero (2005) the palatability of water with TDS less than 600mg/L is generally considered to be good whereas water with TDS greater than 1200mg/L becomes increasingly unpalatable. It is good to know the values were high compared with WHO guideline value of 100mg/L. A significant presence of anions like chloride and sulphate is also observed in the water samples. It has been observed that high amount of sulphate in drinking water causes diarrhea (Obi and Okocha, 2007). It was also found out that the concentration of sulphate in the samples fell within the prescribed limit but the chloride content is much higher than the permitted values of WHO.

Table 2 shows the bacteriological quality of pipe bore water used for drinking in Rufus Giwa Polytechnic, Owo. The total mesophilic count ranged between 2.6 x 10⁴ - 3.3X10⁴ cfu/ml, while total coliform count ranged between 1.1. x 10³ to 2.0X10³ cfu/ml. The total mesophilic count for all the water samples was generally high exceeding the limit of 1.0X10² cfu/ml for water (Ajala et al; 2009).

The fecal coliform counts per 100ml of drinking water should be zero (WHO, 1987) but the values from this study for the water samples exceed the WHO standard limit for water. The result compared favorably with the reports of Obi and Okocha (2006) which indicates that the presence of bushes and shrubs might likely harbor fecal contaminating agents.

Table 2: Bacteriological quality of pipe-borne water used for drinking in Rufus Giwa Polytechnic, Owo, Ondo State, Nigeria

Water Source	Total Mesophilic Count (10 ⁴ cfu/ml)	Total coliform count (10 ³ cfu/ml)
BOYHOS	3.2x10 ⁴	1.1x10 ³
GIRLHOS	2.8x10 ⁴	1.6x10 ³
MAINTE	3.3 x10 ⁴	2.0 x10 ³
RECOFF	2.6x10 ⁴	1.4x10 ³

Key: The water codes were: BOYHOS (Boys hostel) GIRLSHOS (Girls hostel) MAINTE (Maintenance), RECOFF (Rector's Office)

Table 3 Shows the morphological and biochemical characteristics of bacterial isolate from pipe borne water sources used for drinking in Rufus Giwa Polytechnic, Owo. The nature and quantity of microbes in the water samples will determine the health risk to consumers after consuming the water. The gram staining reaction of the bacterial isolates showed that gram negative bacteria were more than the gram positive ones. This is in agreement with previous studies where most bacteria found in the drinking water were gram negative (Mavridou,1992).The biochemical characteristics of the isolates obtained from the water samples showed that the isolates were common to those found in the aquatic environment when their characteristics were compared with those of the known taxa in the bergey's manual of determinative bacteriology (Cheesebrough, 2003).The identified isolates include *Staphylococcus spp*, *Serratia spp*, *Klebsiella ssp*, *Streptococcus spp*,*Pseudomonas spp*, *E.coli*, *Enterobacter spp*, *Acinetobacter spp*,*Proteus spp*, *Bacillus spp*, *Salmonella spp* which were related to those identified by Ajala et al (2009).

Table 3: Morphological and biochemical characteristics of bacterial isolates from pipe borne water used for drinking in Rufus Giwa Polytechnic, Owo

Biochemical Tests/Isolates	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K
Gram Staining	+ve	-ve	-ve	-ve	tve	-ve	-ve	-ve	-ve	+ve	-ve
Catalase	+ve	+ve	+ve	+ve	+ve	+ve	+ve	+ve	+ve	-ve	+ve
Oxidase	-ve	-ve	-ve	-ve	tve	+ve	-ve	-ve	-ve	+ve	-ve
Coagulase	+ve	-ve	-ve	-ve	-ve	-ve	-ve	-ve	-ve	+ve	-ve
Urease	-ve	tve	tve	-ve	-ve	-ve	-ve	+ve	-ve	-ve	-ve
Motility	-ve	+ve	+ve	+ve	-ve	+ve	+ve	-ve	-ve	-ve	+ve
Lactose	Aa	Aa	AG	AG	A	-ve	AG	AG	-ve	-ve	A
Manitol	Aa	AG	AG	AG	A	AG	AG	AG	-ve	A	AG
Sucrose	AG	AG	A	AG	-ve	A	AG	AG	-ve	-ve	AG
Glucose	AG	AG	A	AG	-ve	A	AG	AG	-ve	AG	A
Pigmentation	creamy	whitish	creamy	Greenish	Moistened color	Shiny grey	creamy	creamy	colorless	colorless	red
Shape	cocci	rod	rod	rods	rods	rods	rods	rods	Rod	cocci	rods
Proposed bacterial species	STP	CIT	PRO	ECL	BAC	PSE	ENT	KLE	ACI	STR	SER

KEY: +ve positive, -ve negative, Aa acid production, AG acid and gas production, STP *Staphylococcus sp*, CIT *Citrobacter sp*, PRO *Proteus sp*, ECL *E.coli*, BAC *Bacillus sp*, PSE *Pseudomonas sp*, ENT *Enterobacter sp*, KLE *Klebsiella sp*, ACI *Acinetobacter sp*, STR *Streptococcus sp*, SER *Serratia sp*

The presence of coliform which are used as index to the potential presence of entero pathogens in water pose a considerable harm to human health (Cheesebrough, 2003).These indicator organisms are undesirable in drinking water as they cause major health problems and call for remedial attention of the water sources. Organisms like *Streptococcus spp*, *Bacillus spp*, and *Staphylococcus spp* have been implicated in gastrointestinal disorders and associated symptoms (Cheesebrough, 2003).Opportunistic pathogens such as *Klebsiella spp*, *Serratia spp*, *Proteus spp*, *Enterobacter spp* were also identified which are known to account for up to 50% of nosocomial infections (Obi and Okocha,2007).Typical examples of such infections and their causative agents are lower respiratory infection (*Klebsiella spp*) gastroenteritis (*E.coli*), septicemia, burn ,wounds (*E. coli*), UTIs (*Enterobacter spp*, *Proteus spp*, *Pseudomonas spp*, *Klebsiella spp*, *Streptococcus spp*)(Cheesebrough, 2003).The level of contamination measured by bacteriological analysis may be a risk especially during an outbreak of diseases like cholera or typhoid (WHO, 2003). Therefore the chlorination of drinking water must be considered and monitored more carefully .Chlorination is considered to be highly effective for virus inactivation if the water has a turbidity (NTU 1, a free chlorine residual of 1mg/l or grater for at least 30minutes) and PH less than 8 (Cheesebrough, 2003).The bacteriological testing of water quality in this study is a technological intervention rather than a facilitating approach supplemented by health education.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

The present investigation has led us to conclude that the quality of water samples subjected to this study was acceptable from majority of the physiochemical parameters while as per the bacteriological quality; the water needs to be heated before its domestic application because it exceeds the standard limit. We recommend that proper sanitary survey; design and implementation of water and /or sanitation project regular disinfections, maintenance and supervision of water sources, and regular bacteriological assessment of all water sources for drinking should be planned and conducted

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